

Evaluation of tourism resources in developing the urban economy (case study: Zahak)

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Abstract

Tourism in today's world economy is an integral part of a serious role in income and Gross National Income (GDP) clean industry is headed Zahak of ancient and historical monuments and especially in terms of strategic location, bordering Afghanistan, regional and international transit, tourism has a privileged situation. The purpose of this study was to identify introducing potential to attract tourists in the border town Zahak (bordering Afghanistan) to tourists aimed to economic development of the city, and provide solutions executive is required. Fusion method in this study document - library and field is. The software, used to test «spearman correlation coefficient», «Somers D test», «Kendall tau be test and Gis, Excel, Spss «t-test for 2 independent means», «Analysis Of Variance » and « Kolmogorov -Smirnov test» is. Preliminary results show there are natural attractions of the region to attract tourists can Zahak to play an important role in the economic development of the city. The most consistent way to achieve economic development in Zahak, identify potential tourism areas and using local communities to engage in this way an effective step in strengthening economic level of economic development is to be removed.

Keywords: Tourism, Economic Development, Empowerment and Attractions, Zahak

Introduction

Today, tourism is the most important economic activity of one of the most important scientific issues of the day. (Movahad, 2008, 1) World Tourism Organization, one of the most powerful glances at the international level for to develop tourism, the tourism economy knows. Effects tremendous tourism in reducing unemployment, increasing income levels, providing energy resources, and thriving crafts market, according to statistics, 10 million people since feeding are just some of the special advantages of addressing this industry. Exchange for kidnapping tourists from 2 to 6 jobs will directly create jobs in sectors including manufacturing and a service for tourists, creating jobs is for 9 to 15 people. (Navrozi and etal, 2012).

"Exploring Sirvan in different lands, a part of human life and the needs of the booming in this century, extensive transport facilities, limitations of human communication between different communities destroyed and therefore tourism as a major issue in human life has been raised. Industry to develop economic, social, cultural and political nation, and has created countless jobs, provide friendship and peace between nations and the promotion of human knowledge is "(Mansouri, 2003). Tourism in the process of becoming a tourist destination, the quality of life, value systems, family relationships, attitudes, traditions, customs, behavior patterns, and many other components of economic, social and cultural influences is These effects can be overpopulation, crowding, use of infrastructure, employment status, impact on earnings and poverty in the community pointed out (Kazemi, 2004) The impact of such a change to be able to establish that the precipitous growth in tourism over the past decade and the future based on its With emphasis economists, technicians and technologists and support for developing countries to strengthen the industry towards sustainable development goals in these countries are allowed With emphasis economists, technicians and technologists and support for developing countries to strengthen the industry towards sustainable development goals in these countries are allowed

This strategy not only in developing countries but also includes the industrial world. Due to the wide variety of tourist community, a group of researchers, the impact of the industry in three categories: economic, environmental and social - are classified cultural At the same time they pointed out that some of the items specified for each class are the same as in other classes overlap (Kazemi, 2004) Due to the influence and impact of tourism on the social and economic structure of society, can be noted The proper facilities and services for economic and social policy can be expanded in a certain period of booming tourism demand will be more Conversely, they cannot demand a more restrictive and more restrictive leverage returns

(absolute champion, 1997). And of course, the best use possible of the effects caused by the Thus the social and economic structure of the different functions that can be important is tourism the study in this area will need.

As the tourism industries speak, while providing comfort and recreational industry, causing economic development income urban communities are also included. The world tourism industry is one of the most successful because of the significant achievements of the lining can be noted the gain of foreign currency revenues, direct and indirect job creation to demonstration of stability and security in the country. Our active and effective for the tourism industry by geographical location , historical and cultural attractions of the potential for various reasons , including lack of facilities to attract tourists then welfare facilities , Iran's tourism industry is not your real position and set apart (Yosfipour, 2002, 45) therefore, tourism can Zahak economic development in the northern city of Sistan and Baluchistan province bordering Afghanistan and Iran and Afghanistan on the transit route is provided.

Theoretical Principles Research

"Tourism and the Greek origin of the word is getting around the Tour means Greek to Spanish and French and has finally found its way to England the following definitions are used in the Oxford Dictionary:

- 1) The place or places where the short travel a lot to see.
- 2) Pass a short trip somewhere.
- 3) Means that large amounts of money through the tourism industry, with foreign tourists who come to earn some countries are.

In general, the word tour is derived from the word tourism means a trip back to the spot and follow a specific itinerary. (Ali Asgari, 1997)« Tourism (Tourism) is the activity or activities that people can relax, work or other reasons outside of their usual travel and at least one night stay for a maximum of one year in succession where the chosen "(Sanai, 1996).

"Tourism is a phenomenon of the distant past, societies have been considered According to the different needs of economic, social, historical, and ... The momentum has continued This phenomenon since the Industrial Revolution, particularly during the last century, has expanded dramatically, Underlying science and technology in international relations and economic development of nations "(Ali Asgari, 1997).

When "Thomas Cook" of London launched his first tour, about 150 years ago, this action over a century and a half of ups and downs and changes, the largest social movement in human history became here goes the next century, the greatest economic, social and cultural wellbeing ". In total, a staggering increase in tourism due to improved communications, increased wealth and prosperity and more leisure is (Bonnie Fee 1995, 15) Tourism or tourism industry since 1950 with great changes that some have called it a revolution tourism this led to the development and maturation of "mass tourism" and in the near future "quality tourism" will become. We have a strong and professional tourism activity worldwide is great So that before the first oil, then placed in a row and then above it is growing (Masumi 2007, 9).

"According to the World Tourism Organization, which is affiliated to the United Nations, tourism is the largest industry in the world" (Lund Berg and others, 1995, 3) The first travel in most countries and regions to exploit its economic interests" (World Tourism Organization 2001, 66) The World Tourism Organization statistics that show offers an important impact on tourism in the global economic system, the third largest industry after oil and automobile industries, dynamic and growing industry is the only industry where the introduction "(Nasser M. 2004). "As a force for social change, tourism has been the impact of the Industrial Revolution. In less than three decades, tourism has transformed the world's view of business ". Today tourism has become one of the greatest levers of economic social change in human history So that the number of international tourists in 1950, which did not exceed 25 million in 1992 have been to over 594 million people . According to the World Tourism Organization predicts the number of tourists in 2010 to one billion people in 2020 to 6/1 billion people will increase (Sacrifice 2004). The magnitude of tourism to create jobs and income is not limited. If the thought of planning and development, direct and indirect benefits of tourism to the economic, social, cultural and political environment and make a significant contribution to play in national development In other words, to promote social justice indicators, improved living standards, prosperity and regional balance lead. In some cases, regional economists, tourism as the only resource deployment and development of less developed regions have seen "(Masumi 2007, 10).

"Cultural environment - social media activity is tourism. Thus, culture and tourism community interact with each other. This discussion is related to two aspects:

- Impact and influence on each other's culture and society, culture and tourism community.
- The impact of tourism on culture and society. "(Ibid. 55).

"The benefits of tourism to the local community and cultural patterns and also bring problems. Social work - cultural tourism, including tourism development in each region are the most important considerations, however, measure the impact of the economic and environmental impact is far more difficult. In countries that are still socially and economically very traditional, very critical of these works are important. Although the incidence of social tourism - cultural, but it should be remembered that in principle lead to the development of any new changes are sought. Tourism is the only source of change in society "(World Tourism Organization 1994, 78-79). Economic consequences usually measurable and manifest contrast, only some of the social costs of tourism are obvious, but in other cases not. In the past, the Dutch capital of Amsterdam was the center of attraction hippie and drug addicts. The city's reputation was tarnished, which is a social cost (Lund Berg and others 1995, 83).

"Social problems caused by drug addiction, alcoholism, crime, and prostitution, as well as the tourists are likely to intensify.

Research suggests that these problems are rarely the main reason for this is that tourism but can they provide developments "(World Tourism Organization 1994, 82).

Materials and Methods

This prospective study was conducted using a comprehensive system approach to research - descriptive analysis. Mostly through literature review and resources related theoretical research has been developed. Then the status of questionnaires and statistical analysis methods were included in the study. Complete field data from the questionnaire were used. This respect between tourists scattered 400 questionnaires, of which 350 questionnaires were returned and analyzed. Cochran formula is used to decide the sample size.

Analysis

Tourist attractions in the city Zahak 38 were identified, of which about 10 attractions and 28 Natural attractions, places of historical, cultural and religious needs. Given the natural attractions are low, but most tourists are attracted. Attractions, historical, cultural and religious are too low given that attract tourists.

Table (1): Composition of tourist attractions and city Zahak

Type	The number	Percent
Total	38	100
Natural	10	26.31
Cultural, historical, religious	28	73.69

References: Administration of Cultural Heritage and Tourism Zahak, 2013

Natural and humans making tourism city Zahak

The map below about 10 natural point of tourism in the city Zahak identified include Chahnimeh first and fourth integrated Baqiyatallah Azam along well in the first half, built a wiki of points that most attracts tourists throughout the year. Dams include (dam Jarykah - Kahak - Zahak and Sistan), the Helmand River, forests (Jazink, Niatak, Tiflak and Shirdal).

Figure (1): natural attractions tourist city Zahak, Source: Authors, 2013.

Spatial structure of historical attractions - cultural Zahak religious city

According to the map, including 28 historical attractions, cultural and religious Zahak were identified in the city.

Figure (2): Natural attractions tourist city Zahak, Source: Authors, 2013

Examine connection between some variables

Evaluation of connection satisfaction collision and another trip to town residents Zahak

To study the connection between two variables, the satisfaction rate of people treated Zahak and another trip to this city «Somers D test» was used.

The results of these tests show that most people are very satisfied with the deal people are traveling back to the city. Most people who have low satisfaction and stop from further travel. This result is due to the significance level of statistical tests for general population and significant relation between sig = 0.000 D. Summers, less than (0.05) of two variables satisfying meet townspeople Zahak and another trip to the city to verify.

Table (2): Evaluation of connection satisfaction collision and another trip to town residents Zahak

Total	Very much	high	Average	Low	Very little		
4.0					100.0	Very little	trip to town residents Zahak
6.1			14.3	100.0		Low	
32.3		76.5	85.7			Average	
40.4	65.3	23.5				high	
17.2	34.7					Very much	
100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	Total	
Amount statistic: 23.635					Level of significance: 0.000		

Source: Authors, 2013

Find out the Connection between gender and the impact of tourism on economic development

To test these two variables test «t-test for 2 independent means» is used, the results of this test show that men have a more positive opinion about the potential impact of tourism on economic development. So the mean male perspective (5) higher than the mean score of women view of (4.33) is. It can therefore be concluded sig = 0.000, given the test is less than the significance level (0.05) and the mean differences between the views of men and women about the impact of the tourism potentials of the economic development of the statistically significant is confirmed.

Table (3): Find out the Connection between gender and the impact of tourism on economic development

Significance level	Amount statistic t	Standard error of the mean	Standard deviation	Average	gender
0.000	9.527	.00000	.00000	5.0000	man
		.06997	.54202	4.3333	Woman

Source: Authors, 2013

Find out the connection between age and abilities of the impact of tourism on economical development

To test the connection between age and the impact of tourism on economical development and test abilities. «Kendall tau b test» was used. The test results show the higher the age, the fewer faith in the abilities of the impact of tourism on economical development. And contrary to what people are younger, their belief in the economic development of the tourism potential impact is greater, given that the result is less than the significance level of the test statistic is the generalizations of indicates a significant relation between the two variables confirm (sig = 0.000) is 0.05.

Table (4): Find out the connection between age and abilities of the impact of tourism on economical development

		Age				Total
		0-14	15-34	35-59	+60	
Tourism impact on economic development	Average				9.5	1.3
	high			42.5	90.5	24.0
	Very much	100.0	100.0	57.5		74.7
Total		100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Amount statistic: -10.216					Level of significance: 0.000	

Source: Authors, 2013

Find out the connection between education and tourism potential impact on economical development

To test the connection between Kendall tests is useless. The results of these tests show the more educated people have higher ability impact of tourism on economical development than they know. Conversely, a decline in tourism and education powers of people believes that they have a very powerful impact on economic development. This result is following the test significance level of less than 0.01, sig = 0.000 generalize able to the target population and significant relation between the two variables is confirmed.

Table (5): Find out the connection between education and tourism potential impact on economical development

Total	education						high	Tourism impact on economic development
	Masters	Bachelor of science	Technician	Diploma	Under diploma	Illiterate		
22.2	100.0	100.0	3.8					
77.8			96.2	100.0	100.0	100.0	Very much	
100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	Total	
Amount statistic:-8962			Level of significance: 0.000					

Source: Authors, 2013

Evaluate the potential impact on tourism related jobs and economic development

To test the connection between respondents' views of their jobs about the potential impact of tourism on economical development, test and analysis of variance were used.

This result is due to the significance level of the test is less than 0.05sig = 0.000 statistically generalize able to the entire population and therefore we can say that a significant connection between the two variables is confirmed.

Table (6): Evaluate the potential impact on tourism related jobs and economic development

Level of significance	Amount statistic f	Average	Job
0.000	455.891	5.0000	Employee
		5.0000	Self-employed
		5.0000	pensionary
		5.0000	Currently studying
		4.8889	Worker
		4.0000	Other

Source: Authors, 2013

Explore the connection between income and potential impact of tourism on economical development

To test the connection between these variables and test «t-test for 2 independent means» is used, the results of this test show that people who earn over one million dollars are less positive about the impact of tourism potentials economic development and people earning less favorable than the impact potentials of tourism in economic development, the conclusion on the significance level of the test) is generalize able to the target population and significant relation between the two variables, sig = 0.000 less 0.05 will be verified.

Table (7): Explore the connection between income and potential impact of tourism on economical development

Level of significance	Amount statistic f	Average	Job
0.000	573.500	5.0000	Less than 3000 thousand Riyals
		5.0000	Between 3000 and 6000 thousand Riyals
		5.0000	Between 6000 thousand to 10 million Rials
		4.0588	Above 10 million Rials

Source: Authors, 2013

First theory:

the optimal use of the abilities and potential of tourism to economical development will Zahak.

To test the hypothesis that the normal state of the variables examined. Test to check the normality of the variables «Kolmogorov-Smirnov test» was used. The results are given in the following table.

Table (8): Evaluation of the normal status variables

Kolmogorov-Smirnov	Standard deviation	Average	Variables	Row
0.000	0.44	3.375	Tourism activities	1
0.002	0.76	2.144	Economic Development	2

Source: Authors, 2013

The results of the test «Kolmogorov-Smirnov test» in connection with the distribution of variable features and capabilities of both tourism and economic development of the show. These two variables have a normal distribution, so nonparametric tests should be used to assess the connection between them.

Examining the connection between usability and capabilities of Tourism and Economic Development

Test was used to assess the connection between these two variables is the **spearman** correlation coefficient. The results of the test «spearman correlation coefficient» show highly variable connection between tourism and economic development of the abilities and abilities of 0.945 and the equation is positive. Which shows a strong positive connection exists between these two variables. The functionality and abilities of the tourist town Zahak greater economic development in the city is higher and vice versa. This result is due to a less than significant level test) is generalize able to the target population. The researcher’s theory is confirmed between the two variables sig = 0.000, 0.01 (features and capabilities, there is a positive significant connection between tourism and economic development.

Table (9): Examining the connection between usability and capabilities of Tourism and Economic Development

Statistics	Value
The Spearman correlation coefficient	0.945
Level of significance	0.000

Source: Authors, 2013

According to the correlation coefficient of two variables 0.945 the following diagram shows a strong positive connection exists between these two variables.

Figure (3): investigate the relationship between features and capabilities of Tourism and Economic Development Source: Authors, 2013

Second theory:

the level of employment and tourism activities Zahak people were in town there is a significant connection.

To check the status of normal variables tourism activity and higher levels of employment and income test «Kolmogorov-Smirnov test» was used. The results of these tests show that the assumption of normality is rejected by these two variables, and so they do not have a normal distribution. Therefore, nonparametric tests were used to test the connection between the two. Here is a test to examine the connection between these two variables has been used is the Spearman correlation test.

Table (10): Evaluation of the normal status variables

Kolmogorov-Smirnov	Standard deviation	Average	Variables	Row
0.000	0.67	1.820	Tourism activities	1
0.000	0.57	1.262	Level of employment and income	2

Source: Authors, 2013

The connection between tourism activity and increased levels of employment and income

The results of the test «spearman correlation coefficient» show highly variable connection between tourism activity and an increase in income and employment levels 0.769 and the equation is positive. So we can say that there is a strong positive connection between these two variables. The higher the level of tourism activity in the area of employment and higher income residents, and vice versa. This result is due to the significance level of the test is less) is generalize able to the target population and the researcher’s hypothesis is confirmed. Among the sig = 0.000, 0.01 (Zahak and increased tourism activity in the employment and income, there is a significant connection.

Table (11): The connection between tourism activity and increased levels of employment and income

Statistics	Values
The Spearman correlation coefficient	0.769
Level of significance	0.000

Source: Authors, 2013

According to the correlation coefficient of two variables 0.769 the graph below shows that the connection is positive.

Figure (4): investigate the relationship between tourism activities and the level of employment and income Source: Authors, 2013

Conclusions

Zahak city due to historical, cultural and natural heritage that is to be hoped that the development of the tourism industry and discovered that:

The first problem is to develop tourism in this city tourist attractions remain unknown. As the first step of this work must be identified and its attraction to tourists frequently presented with advertising. Another point that should be addressed in the planning principles for the development of urban economy with tourism. If appropriate facilities are provided, and a logical approach to analyze of various aspects of the future of this region can be transformed into a tourist hub. Given the high unemployment rate in the city's tourism industry can create jobs for the unemployed. Tubs are engaged in work related services to tourists. And with lead to the economic development of the region and provided Zahak. Which will provide the background to the economic development of the country? Others who should be serious consideration on the development of motels, hotels, recreational facilities and services to provide greater urban area Zahak attraction to tourists in Zahak more time to stop. Thereby providing improved hotel facilities and local attractions, tourists will provide long life. Because more tourists are longer lasting, more Zahak will result in the economic development of the city. Note the development of crafts. The development of crafts can be fertile ground for job creation and revenue. Both the copacetic this city a positive impact. And, as creativity can be a symbol of lifestyle, attitudes and manners of the natives. Development and crafts, a good advertisement for the city will introduce the customs. The results of the first research hypothesis based on the optimal use of the capabilities and potential of tourism to economic development will Zahak. The intensity of the relationship between the two variables is 0.945 usability and capabilities of tourism and economic development. And the relationship is positive. Which indicates a strong positive relationship exists between these two variables. The functionality and capabilities of the tourist town Zahak further economic development in the city is higher and vice versa.

The results of the second hypothesis test between tourism activities employment and income levels in the city Zahak significant connection exists. Shows the connection between two variables, severity, tourism activities and increasing income and employment levels 0.769 and the equation is positive. So we can say that there is a strong positive connection between these two variables. The higher the level of tourism activity in the area of employment and higher income residents, and vice versa.

Suggestions

- development seminars and meetings with other agencies and officials associated with the investment in the tourism industry and entrepreneurs
- develop and strengthen the publicity and information programs to introduce the province's natural attractions, historical and cultural features of the hospitality of the people of the City Zahak for employment and income for residents of The main focus of the activities on sampling
- also review the types and how to take advantage of people's contributions to the development, preparation and implementation of urban plans and equipment beyond the city terms of tourist facilities and services

necessary Specialists from various institutions in the areas of rehabilitation and development measures are necessary.

inviting local and foreign investors to invest in construction of facilities and special rates for hotels, residential complexes, resorts, forest, creating sports fields, and ...

tourist resources and tourist attractions such as the free use of the potential of cultural and historical Zahak economic use of resources, tourism and the tourism industry categories - commercial plant and related workshops

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